

ECONOMICS

MANAGER'S WORK METHODS AND MODERN APPROACHES

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Abstract

Different perception strategies are stable images, which were worked out among representatives of some particular ethnic societies and are revealed in relations between the components of cognitive and emotional evaluations. During the perception of other cultures and people of different races, some particular keys exist, through which the human freely perceives the representatives of his / her circle, but the keys are not operational while the representatives of other cultures are about to be perceived. Differently strategies exist, such as the stereotypes of national conduct and stereotypes of perception. Thanks to stereotypes of national conduct (stable, schematic models of conduct) the situations are split into types, and ethnic micro-groups choose the answer to managerial impact on the organization. The leader's knowledge of specific conduct properties allows them to preliminarily determine the actions and responses of staff individuals and representatives of ethnic micro-groups.

Keywords: Manager, work methods, modern approaches, management level, management models.

Introduction. The position of senior managers is very difficult due to their work's high volume and stressful nature. A person in this position is usually solitary. This is why top executives are highly paid. Heads of the highest level of management include the company president, vice president, rector in higher education, etc. According to research, senior managers spend 59-61% of their working time on planned discussions and meetings, unplanned meetings require 10% of their working time, and work on documents requires 20-22%. They spend the rest of their time on the phone and visiting the facility.

Discussion. Organizations often participate in community life voluntarily. For example, Procter & Gamble (USA) withdrew Riley tampons from sale in 1980 when it discovered that they could cause shock due to toxicity. Johnson & Johnson took similar steps when Tylenol capsules were found to contain traces of cyanide. The decision to withdraw this product from production cost the company approximately (estimated) 50 million dollars. „Ford Motor“ company behaved completely differently to the "Pinto" case. After three women were killed in their 1973 Pinto cars that exploded after a rear-end collision, Ford was taken to court. The firm's management claimed to have strictly followed federal regulations and gone to great lengths (adding \$11 in detail) to prevent the fuel system from burning. But the following was established in the mentioned case:

- 1) the management of the firm should have known about the dangers of the fuel system according to the report received during the relevant inspection;
- 2) The „Pinto“ model could not withstand a 50 km/s impact without the high probability of destroying (breaking) the gas tank;
- 3) The project's chief engineer testified that his numerous written and verbal reminders to the firm's management about Pinto's lack of safety were ignored and he was reassigned to a job unrelated to the federal standards issues. An example of social responsibility

for raising the educational level in society is the Apple Computer company, which donated computer systems to more than 9,000 primary and secondary schools. IBM also donated computer systems to many American universities.

Therefore, organizations (firms) should direct part of their resources and efforts for the benefit of the local communities in which the firm and its units operate. Organizations will not be able to work for long in the conditions of conflict with their environment. For effective management, the organization must be able to adapt to the social environment, so that this environment becomes more favorable for the organization. Spending on social responsibility is justified by the improvement of various segments of society, as well as by improving the public's relationship with the company. All this leads to the loyalty of consumers (buyers) to the producers of products, the reduction of the level of regulatory intervention of the state in business, and the general improvement of the state of society.

The main problem of social responsibility is personal values. People who believe that organizations should strive to maximize profits place a high value on profit maximization, and efficiency, and a low value on altruism. Such people believe that an organization is behaving correctly and socially responsible as long as its actions correspond to a given system of values. To choose favor of the right behavior, it is important to have a basic understanding of ethics. Ethics is directly related to the principles that define right and wrong behavior. But business ethics will concern not only the problem of socially responsible behavior. It concentrates on a wide range of behavior options for the governing (managing subject) and governed (managing object) subsystems.

Moreover, the focus of attention of ethics is both the goals and the means used to achieve them by both one and the other subsystem. For example, almost all Americans consider it unethical to bribe a foreign official to obtain a lucrative contract. In this case, the

means are unethical. However, entering into a contract for fur seals without a bribe could be seen as misconduct in a country where wildlife protection is highly valued. Therefore, the use of cat fur is unethical as such behavior, although not against the law, is contrary to personal values and constitutes an action that cannot be endorsed.

Ethical problems in business have a direct relationship with conflict situations, which are determined by the ratio between the organization's income, costs, and profit indicators and its social responsibility indicators, which are expressed through relationships with other people, both within the organization and in society.

With senior managers often exhibiting unethical corporate behavior, anyone in an organization can also act unethically. Consider the following situations: a purchasing agent is offered a case of fine wine by one of the suppliers with whom he does business; Some workers from the organization conduct international telephone conversations about personal matters; The worker can use for himself what is intended for the organization and take it home. Here are just a few of the ethical dilemmas that everyone can face at work. In the given examples, there is no violation of the law, but the corresponding actions can be described as wrong in many cases. Unethical actions of people in clear violation of the law include falsification of documents that are sent to state regulation services, appropriation of funds, racial discrimination, etc. Actions in violation of the law in the fields of environmental pollution, product safety, and labor safety should also be considered unethical.

Conclusion. In Georgian business, unfortunately, it is still too early to talk about solving the problems of social responsibility and ethics at the first level. Even in developed market economy countries, signs of the expansion of unethical business practices can be observed recently. Managers cite the following as the reason for this: aggravation of the competitive struggle; providing managers with inappropriate remuneration

for ethical behavior; reducing the importance of ethics in society, etc.

Increasing the ethics of managers and ordinary workers depends a lot on modern management. In this regard, the development of ethical standards, the creation of ethics committees, conducting social audits, and training in ethical behavior are of great importance.

Organizations create standing ethics committees (commissions) to evaluate daily practices. Almost all members of such committees are top-level managers. Some organizations do not create such a committee; instead, they hire a business ethics professional called an ethics attorney. The function of the ethics lawyer is to develop a conclusion on ethical issues related to the actions of the organization, as well as to perform the function of the "social conscience" of the organization.

The task of social audits is to compile and evaluate reports on the social impact of the organization's actions and programs. Proponents of social auditing assume that this type of reporting provides a complete picture of the organization's level of social responsibility.

Teaching managers and ordinary workers the rules of ethical behavior is another approach used by organizations to increase the indicators of ethical behavior. Employees are introduced to business ethics and raise their awareness of ethical issues they may face.

Modern management provides an opportunity for organizations to raise their ethical standards and successfully implement various social responsibility tasks.

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